

A Deep Dive into Effects of Structural Bias on CMA-ES Performance along Affine Trajectories: Supplemental Material

Niki van Stein¹[0000-0002-0013-7969], Sarah L. Thomson²[0000-0001-6971-7817],
and Anna V. Kononova¹[0000-0002-4138-7024]

¹ LIACS, Leiden University, Einsteinweg 55, 2333 CC Leiden, Netherlands
{n.van.stein,a.kononova}@liacs.leidenuniv.nl

² Edinburgh Napier University, United Kingdom
s.thomson4@napier.ac.uk

1 CMAES Configurations

After doing the bias sweep, we consider the top-scoring CMA-ES configurations in four bias categories for the subsequent experiments on algorithm performance. These are: **bounds** (Table 1); **centre** (Table 2); **uniform/none** (Table 3) and **mixed** (Table 4).

2 BBOB Functions

In Figure 1 we show visualisations of the 2D BBOB functions which are used as constituents for the affine pairs in the study: Sphere (1a); separable Rastrign (1b); non-separable Rastrign (1c); Weierstrass (1d); and Gallagher’s Gaussian 101-me Peaks function (1e).

(a) Sphere

(b) Separable Rastrigin

(c) Non-separable Rastrigin

(d) Weierstrass

(e) Gallagher's Gaussian 101-me Peaks

Fig. 1: The selected BBOB functions visualised in 2D

Table 1: Top CMAES configurations for the bias class: **bounds**. Denoted in brackets after each module setting is the average effect (SHAP value) of choosing the respective option versus all other choices (keeping the rest of the settings the same).

active	covariance	elitist	orthogonal	sequential	threshold	sigma	boundcorr	mirrored	base sampler	weights	option	local restart	stepadapt
False (0.00)	False (1.00)	True (0.93)	True (0.00)	False (0.00)	True (0.00)	False (0.00)	saturate (0.60)	mirrored (0.60)	halton (0.00)	1/2'ambda (0.00)	BIPOP (0.00)	BIPOP (0.00)	tpa (0.00)
True (0.00)	False (0.60)	True (1.00)	False (0.00)	True (0.00)	True (0.00)	False (0.00)	saturate (0.97)	mirrored (0.97)	sobol (0.00)	1/2'ambda (0.00)	IPOP (0.00)	IPOP (0.00)	mnr (0.20)
True (0.00)	False (0.88)	True (1.00)	False (0.00)	True (0.00)	True (0.00)	False (0.00)	saturate (0.99)	mirrored (0.99)	sobol (0.00)	default (0.00)	IPOP (0.00)	IPOP (0.00)	mnr (0.33)
True (0.00)	False (0.94)	True (1.00)	False (0.19)	True (0.00)	False (0.00)	False (0.00)	saturate (0.93)	mirrored (0.93)	sobol (0.00)	1/2'ambda (0.00)	IPOP (0.00)	IPOP (0.00)	mnr (0.43)
True (0.00)	False (1.00)	True (1.00)	False (1.00)	True (0.00)	False (0.00)	False (0.00)	saturate (0.97)	mirrored (0.97)	sobol (0.00)	equal (0.00)	IPOP (0.00)	IPOP (0.00)	mnr (0.77)
True (0.00)	False (1.00)	True (1.00)	False (1.00)	True (0.00)	False (0.00)	False (0.00)	saturate (0.99)	mirrored (0.99)	sobol (0.00)	default (0.00)	IPOP (0.00)	IPOP (0.00)	mnr (0.60)
True (0.00)	False (1.00)	True (1.00)	False (0.00)	True (0.00)	True (0.00)	False (0.00)	saturate (0.94)	mirrored (0.94)	sobol (0.00)	1/2'ambda (0.00)	IPOP (0.00)	IPOP (0.00)	tpa (0.20)
True (0.00)	False (1.00)	True (1.00)	False (0.00)	True (0.00)	True (0.00)	False (0.00)	saturate (0.98)	mirrored (0.98)	sobol (0.00)	default (0.00)	IPOP (0.00)	IPOP (0.00)	tpa (0.33)
True (0.00)	False (0.86)	True (1.00)	False (1.00)	True (0.00)	False (0.00)	True (0.00)	saturate (0.98)	nan (0.00)	halton (0.00)	default (0.00)	IPOP (0.00)	IPOP (0.00)	mnr (0.53)
True (0.00)	False (1.00)	True (1.00)	False (0.00)	True (0.00)	True (0.00)	True (0.00)	saturate (0.99)	nan (0.00)	halton (0.00)	1/2'ambda (0.00)	IPOP (0.50)	IPOP (0.50)	tpa (0.21)
True (0.00)	False (1.00)	True (1.00)	False (0.00)	True (0.00)	True (0.00)	True (0.00)	saturate (0.99)	nan (0.00)	halton (0.00)	equal (0.00)	IPOP (0.00)	IPOP (0.00)	tpa (0.50)
True (0.00)	False (1.00)	True (1.00)	False (1.00)	True (0.00)	False (0.00)	False (0.00)	saturate (1.00)	mirrored (1.00)	sobol (0.00)	equal (0.00)	IPOP (0.00)	IPOP (0.00)	tpa (0.77)
True (0.00)	False (1.00)	True (1.00)	False (0.00)	True (0.00)	True (0.00)	True (0.00)	saturate (0.99)	nan (0.00)	halton (0.00)	default (0.00)	IPOP (0.50)	IPOP (0.50)	tpa (0.30)
True (0.00)	False (1.00)	True (1.00)	False (1.00)	True (0.00)	False (0.00)	True (0.00)	saturate (1.00)	nan (0.00)	halton (0.00)	1/2'ambda (0.00)	IPOP (0.50)	IPOP (0.50)	tpa (0.48)
False (0.97)	True (0.97)	True (0.42)	True (0.08)	False (0.31)	True (0.97)	False (0.03)	saturate (0.92)	nan (0.05)	gaussian (0.07)	1/2'ambda (0.46)	nan (0.90)	nan (0.90)	psr (0.69)
False (0.97)	True (0.97)	True (0.64)	True (0.21)	False (0.19)	True (0.97)	False (0.01)	saturate (0.94)	pairwise (0.04)	sobol (0.05)	1/2'ambda (0.46)	nan (0.92)	nan (0.92)	psr (0.63)
False (0.84)	True (0.97)	True (0.83)	False (0.97)	True (0.09)	False (0.10)	True (0.05)	saturate (0.97)	pairwise (0.07)	halton (0.19)	default (0.30)	nan (0.96)	nan (0.96)	mnr (0.84)
False (0.93)	True (0.97)	True (0.42)	False (0.24)	True (0.15)	True (0.10)	False (0.29)	saturate (0.96)	mirrored (0.16)	sobol (0.21)	default (0.59)	nan (0.97)	nan (0.97)	mnr (0.73)
False (0.98)	True (0.98)	True (0.05)	True (0.21)	False (0.05)	True (0.98)	True (0.00)	saturate (0.83)	nan (0.10)	halton (0.18)	1/2'ambda (0.78)	nan (0.90)	nan (0.90)	lpxnes (0.72)
False (0.98)	True (0.98)	True (0.05)	True (0.21)	False (0.05)	True (0.98)	False (0.00)	saturate (0.83)	nan (0.10)	halton (0.18)	1/2'ambda (0.78)	nan (0.90)	nan (0.90)	lpxnes (0.56)
False (0.77)	True (0.98)	True (0.77)	False (0.31)	True (0.15)	True (0.09)	True (0.14)	saturate (0.94)	mirrored (0.05)	sobol (0.02)	1/2'ambda (0.39)	nan (0.59)	nan (0.59)	psr (0.68)
False (0.25)	True (0.98)	True (0.14)	True (0.19)	False (0.52)	True (0.69)	False (0.14)	saturate (0.97)	pairwise (0.09)	gaussian (0.15)	default (0.35)	nan (0.88)	nan (0.88)	mnr (0.77)

Table 2: Top CMAES configurations for the bias class: **centre**
 Denoted in brackets after each module setting is the average effect (SHAP value) of choosing the respective option versus all other choices (keeping the rest of the settings the same).

active	covariance	elitist	orthogonal	sequential	threshold	sigma	boundcorr	mirrored	base sampler	weights	option	local restart	stepadapt
True (0.02)	False (0.02)	True (0.01)	True (0.04)	False (0.04)	True (0.88)	True (0.04)	mirror (0.41)	pairwise (0.02)	halton (0.02)	equal (0.08)	IPOP (0.04)	mxnes (0.60)	
False (0.04)	False (0.02)	False (1.00)	True (0.07)	False (0.01)	True (0.07)	True (0.02)	toroidal (0.40)	mirrored (0.12)	gaussian (0.01)	equal (0.02)	BIPOP (0.05)	csa (0.12)	
True (0.02)	False (0.05)	False (0.41)	False (0.02)	False (0.01)	True (0.13)	True (0.02)	uniform (0.43)	pairwise (0.01)	halton (0.02)	equal (0.21)	nan (0.05)	xnes (0.12)	
False (0.04)	False (0.02)	False (0.59)	True (0.11)	False (0.02)	True (0.07)	True (0.02)	toroidal (0.40)	mirrored (0.12)	gaussian (0.01)	equal (0.02)	IPOP (0.05)	csa (0.13)	
True (0.01)	False (0.06)	True (0.87)	True (0.04)	True (0.01)	False (0.09)	True (0.19)	uniform (0.42)	mirrored (0.01)	sobol (0.01)	equal (0.02)	BIPOP (0.26)	mxnes (0.28)	
True (0.02)	False (0.08)	True (0.01)	False (0.87)	False (0.02)	False (0.01)	False (0.00)	toroidal (0.37)	pairwise (0.02)	halton (0.01)	equal (0.04)	IPOP (0.09)	mxnes (0.33)	
True (0.00)	False (0.03)	True (0.07)	True (0.99)	True (0.01)	False (0.99)	False (0.02)	cotn (0.22)	nan (0.04)	sobol (0.01)	default (0.05)	IPOP (0.78)	msr (0.41)	
False (0.01)	False (0.22)	True (0.05)	True (0.85)	True (0.01)	False (0.82)	True (0.01)	mirror (0.26)	mirrored (0.06)	halton (0.01)	default (0.04)	IPOP (0.77)	csa (0.09)	
False (0.01)	False (0.02)	True (0.03)	True (0.99)	True (0.06)	False (1.00)	False (0.02)	cotn (0.41)	pairwise (0.02)	sobol (0.02)	equal (0.34)	IPOP (0.97)	msr (0.18)	
True (0.01)	False (0.08)	True (0.01)	False (0.01)	False (0.01)	True (0.01)	True (0.02)	mirror (0.38)	mirrored (0.01)	sobol (0.01)	equal (0.25)	IPOP (0.10)	mxnes (0.62)	
False (0.01)	False (0.00)	True (0.04)	True (0.05)	True (0.01)	True (0.46)	True (0.01)	uniform (0.41)	mirrored (0.04)	halton (0.01)	equal (0.15)	IPOP (0.11)	mxnes (0.59)	
False (0.02)	False (0.02)	True (0.02)	True (0.07)	True (0.01)	True (0.29)	False (0.03)	toroidal (0.44)	mirrored (0.01)	sobol (0.01)	default (0.06)	IPOP (0.32)	mxnes (0.78)	
True (0.01)	False (0.04)	True (0.02)	False (0.03)	False (0.01)	True (0.02)	False (0.02)	uniform (0.39)	mirrored (0.01)	halton (0.01)	equal (0.14)	IPOP (0.12)	mxnes (0.57)	
True (0.07)	True (0.05)	True (0.01)	True (0.10)	False (0.05)	True (0.89)	False (0.00)	toroidal (0.40)	nan (0.01)	sobol (0.01)	equal (0.01)	nan (0.01)	xnes (0.03)	
True (0.01)	False (0.03)	True (0.04)	True (0.90)	False (0.01)	False (0.93)	True (0.02)	mirror (0.38)	mirrored (0.05)	sobol (0.00)	equal (0.18)	IPOP (1.00)	msr (0.44)	
True (0.01)	False (0.08)	True (0.13)	True (0.94)	True (0.05)	False (0.99)	False (0.01)	cotn (0.20)	nan (0.04)	sobol (0.03)	equal (0.05)	IPOP (0.39)	msr (0.51)	
False (0.01)	False (0.24)	True (0.97)	True (0.39)	False (0.01)	False (0.80)	False (0.04)	cotn (0.79)	mirrored (0.46)	gaussian (0.01)	equal (0.22)	BIPOP (0.19)	xnes (0.39)	
True (0.00)	False (0.07)	True (0.14)	True (1.00)	False (0.02)	False (1.00)	True (0.01)	saturne (0.22)	mirrored (0.15)	gaussian (0.01)	default (0.04)	nan (0.70)	mxnes (0.81)	
False (0.01)	True (0.01)	False (0.01)	True (0.23)	False (0.02)	True (0.99)	False (0.10)	uniform (0.40)	nan (0.02)	sobol (0.05)	default (0.06)	IPOP (0.05)	xnes (0.11)	
True (0.09)	False (0.97)	True (0.97)	False (0.97)	False (0.06)	False (0.23)	False (0.03)	toroidal (0.44)	nan (0.03)	halton (0.04)	equal (0.65)	nan (0.97)	csa (0.96)	

Table 3: Top CMAES configurations for the bias class: **uniform/none**
 Denoted in brackets after each module setting is the average effect (SHAP value) of choosing the respective option versus all other choices (keeping the rest of the settings the same).

active	covariance	elitist	orthogonal	sequential	threshold	sigma	boundcorr	mirrored	base sampler	weights option	local restart	stepadapt
False (0.05)	False (0.98)	True (0.97)	True (0.06)	True (0.04)	True (0.98)	False (0.07)	mirror (0.50)	pairwise (0.20)	sobol (0.22)	default (0.30)	IPOP (0.98)	tpa (0.45)
True (0.04)	False (0.98)	True (0.98)	False (0.29)	True (0.12)	True (0.17)	True (0.14)	mirror (0.50)	pairwise (0.05)	gaussian (0.07)	$1/2'$ ambda (0.09)	IPOP (0.98)	csa (0.32)
True (0.38)	False (0.98)	True (0.98)	False (0.06)	True (0.01)	True (0.09)	True (0.35)	mirror (0.47)	pairwise (0.04)	gaussian (0.04)	default (0.07)	IPOP (0.98)	tpa (0.38)
True (0.07)	False (0.98)	True (0.98)	False (0.03)	False (0.04)	True (0.08)	False (0.07)	toroidal (0.43)	mirrored (0.13)	sobol (0.04)	equal (0.73)	nan (0.73)	csa (0.94)
True (0.53)	True (0.20)	False (0.58)	False (0.25)	False (0.47)	False (0.08)	True (0.13)	saturate (0.94)	pairwise (0.47)	sobol (0.12)	$1/2'$ ambda (0.66)	nan (0.31)	tpa (0.44)
False (0.19)	False (0.97)	True (0.87)	True (0.14)	True (0.07)	True (0.97)	True (0.05)	mirror (0.47)	nan (0.08)	gaussian (0.03)	equal (0.90)	nan (0.60)	csa (0.80)
True (0.06)	False (0.97)	True (0.97)	False (0.21)	True (0.22)	True (0.15)	True (0.01)	cotn (0.80)	pairwise (0.13)	halton (0.13)	default (0.28)	nan (0.15)	tpa (0.42)
True (0.23)	True (0.97)	False (0.97)	True (0.03)	True (0.15)	True (0.97)	False (0.14)	saturate (0.90)	nan (0.10)	gaussian (0.11)	$1/2'$ ambda (0.22)	nan (0.38)	csa (0.48)
True (0.07)	False (0.83)	True (0.97)	False (0.08)	False (0.05)	True (0.04)	True (0.03)	mirror (0.44)	mirrored (0.03)	halton (0.15)	equal (0.11)	IPOP (0.97)	msr (0.70)

Table 4: Top CMAES configurations for the bias class: **mixed**
 Denoted in brackets after each module setting is the average effect (SHAP value) of choosing the respective option versus all other choices (keeping the rest of the settings the same).

active	covariance	elitist	orthogonal	sequential	threshold	sigma	boundcorr	mirrored	base sampler	weights option	local restart	stepadapt
True (0.00)	False (1.00)	True (1.00)	False (0.00)	True (0.00)	True (0.00)	True (0.00)	saturate (0.96)	nan (0.00)	halton (0.00)	equal (0.00)	IPOP (0.00)	msr (0.50)
True (0.00)	False (0.92)	True (1.00)	False (0.00)	True (0.00)	True (0.00)	True (0.00)	saturate (0.98)	nan (0.00)	halton (0.00)	default (0.00)	IPOP (0.00)	msr (0.30)
True (0.00)	False (0.62)	True (1.00)	False (1.00)	True (0.00)	False (0.00)	True (0.00)	saturate (0.97)	nan (0.00)	halton (0.00)	$1/2'ambda$ (0.00)	IPOP (0.00)	msr (0.48)
True (0.00)	False (1.00)	True (1.00)	False (0.00)	True (0.00)	True (0.00)	False (0.00)	saturate (1.00)	mirrored (0.00)	sobol (0.00)	equal (0.00)	IPOP (0.00)	tpa (0.53)
False (0.16)	True (1.00)	True (0.03)	True (1.00)	True (0.01)	False (1.00)	False (0.02)	saturate (0.15)	mirrored (0.02)	sobol (0.05)	default (0.29)	IPOP (0.30)	msr (0.50)
False (0.42)	False (0.12)	False (0.98)	False (0.94)	True (0.07)	False (0.37)	True (0.00)	saturate (0.88)	nan (0.15)	halton (0.15)	$1/2'ambda$ (0.98)	nan (0.08)	lpxnes (0.68)
False (0.42)	False (0.12)	False (0.98)	False (0.94)	True (0.07)	False (0.37)	False (0.00)	saturate (0.88)	nan (0.15)	halton (0.15)	$1/2'ambda$ (0.98)	nan (0.08)	lpxnes (0.61)